

Introduction to Data FAIRification

Version 1.0

The content for this course was based on materials developed for and insights gained from the [W1 FAIRification Lab: Applying FAIR Principles to Enhance Data Stewardship workshop](#), conducted at the [BIO.IT World Conference](#) in April 2025 in Boston, Massachusetts.

Course Objectives

In this course, you will learn how to FAIRify scientific datasets. The course is comprised of three modules that will:

1. Introduce you to the nature of FAIR Data and teach you how Data FAIRification is performed
2. Show you how to assess the FAIRness of Datasets
3. Provide you an illustrative example of Data FAIRification

Module 1

FAIRplus FAIRification Framework—Features

FAIRification Frameworks

- Provide a structured, step-by-step process for transforming data to align with the FAIR Principles.

The FAIRplus FAIRification Framework

- Provides a practical, step-by-step approach to transforming data into FAIR-compliant assets. A flexible, scalable, and domain-agnostic approach, making it a sustainable solution for enhancing FAIR data practices across disciplines and is not limited to the life sciences.
- Agnostic of any specific implementation solutions, methodologies, or tools, allowing users to leverage the resources already at their disposal rather than being forced to invest in solutions that may not be right.
- Guidance through the FAIRification process, from assessing the current state of the data to publishing it in FAIR-compliant repositories.
 - Manages the associated FAIRification activities.
- Optimizes use of available resources by focused prioritization of needs, based on a thorough analysis of the unique and specific FAIR challenges of each specific project.
- Encourages stakeholder engagement and iterative refinement.

FAIRification Framework—Components

The FAIRification Process: Reusable process for FAIRification activities in four phases:

- Goal Definition
- Initial Project Examination
- An Iterative, Cyclical FAIRification
- Post-FAIRification Review Phase

The FAIRification Template: Stepwise decomposition of the process

- Provides an outline of possible FAIRification aspects for a dataset
- Modified based on implementation and tool preferences of the organization

The FAIRification Workplan:

- Organizes the necessary FAIRification activities of the project

FAIRification Framework—Components

FAIRification Framework—Process

The FAIRification Framework—Template

FAIRification Steps

- 1. Define FAIRification Goals:** These should be translatable into concrete tasks, with clearly defined scope or endpoint and provide cost/benefit (see following examples on next slide).
- 2. Project Examination:** Identify the data requirements and FAIRification capabilities and resources and create the FAIRification backlog.
- 3. Iterative FAIRification Cycles:** Design of activities, implementation of activities, and assessment cycles using the customizable FAIRification Template (this is optional). Create and use a workplan to manage the activity in the cycles, listed in the backlog.
- 4. Post FAIRification Review:** Assess the dataset FAIRness after FAIRification.

Examples of Well-Defined FAIRification Goals

- Convert dataset from proprietary to open format
- Markup semantically to reduce free text descriptors
- Identify gaps in current metadata annotations and pick the best ontologies to fill them
- Make metadata findable/searchable
- Publish data in open archives and comply with community data standards so that other researchers can find and reuse the compound and bioassay data
- Map the data dictionary to CDISC and appropriate domain-relevant ontologies to facilitate data interoperability and enable sharing of metadata in data catalogues and repositories to make the data more findable
- Publish data in open archives and comply with community data standards so that other researchers can find and reuse the compound and bioassay data
- Map the data dictionary to CDISC and appropriate domain-relevant ontologies to facilitate data interoperability and enable sharing of metadata in data catalogues and repositories to make the data more findable
- Provide advice and information to the consortium members so they can decide on the type of licensing for publicly sharing the data and clarifying the possible reuse of the data
- Promote public access, data dissemination, and sharing of project datasets
- Standardize and develop workflows involving data archiving process for terminated sub-projects
- Improve findability of project metadata for external researcher through publication of metadata in the IMI Data Catalog

Module 1 Supplementary Information

- The [FAIRplus FAIRification Framework](#) was developed by the FAIRplus project, funded by the [European Union's Innovative Medicines Initiative \(IMI\)](#). It provides a practical, step-by-step approach to FAIRify data, particularly (but not limited to) in the life sciences domain.
- The FAIRification Framework consists of three components:
 - [The FAIRification Process](#) is the reusable process that outlines the main phases of a FAIRification activity.
 - [The FAIRification Template](#) breaks down the key elements of the process into a series of steps to follow when undertaking a FAIR transformation.
 - [The FAIRification Workplan Layout](#) provides a structure for organizing FAIR implementation work tailored to the needs of a specific project.
- The FAIRplus project also released the [FAIRplus Cookbook](#), a collection of practical guides for FAIRifying data. The Cookbook provides:
 - Assessment of FAIR levels of projects and data, identification of approaches to FAIRification that work in the real world. The framework successfully FAIRified data from 20 IMI projects and internal EFPIA datasets
 - Best practices on data FAIRification and FAIR data management. An approach to changing data management culture by encouraging more data to be *born FAIR*.
 - A practical, step-by-step approach to transforming data into FAIR-compliant assets. The flexible, scalable, and domain-agnostic approach makes it a sustainable solution for enhancing FAIR data practices across disciplines and is not limited to the life sciences.
 - An approach agnostic of any specific implementation solutions, methodologies, or tools, allows users to leverage the resources already at their disposal rather than being forced to invest in solutions that may not be right.
 - Guidance throughout the FAIRification process, from assessing the current state of the data to publishing it in FAIR-compliant repositories.
 - Optimization of available resources by focused prioritization of needs, based on a thorough analysis of the unique and specific FAIR challenges of each specific project. Encourages stakeholder engagement and iterative refinement.

Module 2

Landscape Data FAIRness Assessment Models

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1. [FAIRplus DSM Model](#)
2. [RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model](#)
3. [GO FAIR Metrics](#)
4. [ARDC FAIR Self-Assessment Tool](#)
5. [FAIRsFAIR Maturity Model](#)
6. [GO FAIR Metrics](#)
7. [EOSC Synergy FAIR Data Maturity Model](#)
8. [Science Europe FAIR Data Checklist](#)
9. [NIST FAIR Framework](#)
10. [OpenAIRE FAIR Resources](#)

FAIRplus Dataset Maturity (DSM) Model

- Intended as a comprehensive reference model for state-of-FAIRness improvement in research datasets
- Best applicable for domains related to life sciences and biomedical research
- Uses the dataset as the unit for FAIR sharing and reuse
- Defines and classifies requirements that constitute an incremental path toward improving FAIRness level for a given research dataset in terms of *Five Levels of Maturity*

FAIRplus-DSM Model Levels of Data Maturity

5	Managed Data Assets	Enterprise Level. Data at this level is optimally managed at the most granular level in an environment offering <i>data governance, master data management and reference data management</i> capabilities.
4	Semantically Typed Data	Cross-community Level. This level focuses on cross-domain interoperability and is meant to be the level required for larger harmonization and integration projects.
3	Standardised Data	Community Level. Data at this level complies with community standard domain models, terminologies and formats, and is hosted in an environment offering searching and retrieval capabilities.
2	Described Data	Project Level. All datasets generated within a project are consistently described against a locally defined schema, controlled terminologies, and hosted in an environment offering data catalogue level searching capabilities.
1	Identifiable Data	Data Object level. Data at this level is identifiable as individual generic data objects and described by generic metadata elements. Hosting environment offers limited retrieval capabilities.
0	Single Use Data	No potential for re-use beyond lifetime of the research project

FAIRplus-DSM Model—Dimensions and Indicators

The model focuses on *three dimensions* of FAIR data maturation:

- **Content-related:** What is reported in the dataset (data) & the dataset descriptor (metadata)?
- **Hosting environment capabilities:** What are the capabilities of the hosting environment that enable and support the use of FAIR data?
- **Representation and format:** How the data object & metadata object are represented and formatted

The *three dimensions* are assessed using the following *three sets of indicators*:

- **Content and Context Indicators:** To ensure the dataset is meaningful and well-documented
- **Representation and Format Indicators:** To ensure the dataset is standardized and technically robust
- **Hosting Capabilities Indicators:** To ensure the dataset is accessible, reliable, and supported by appropriate infrastructure

FAIRplus-DSM Model Indicators and Components

FAIRplus-DSM Assessment Tool

- [The FAIRplus-DSM Assessment Tool](#) is the reference implementation for determining dataset maturity in terms of indicators for *three* dimensions: content and context, representation and format, and hosting.
- Presents a wizard interface on a dataset to guide the user through a set of questions that determine the maturity in terms of indicators of the *three* dimensions of the dataset.
- On completion of the questionnaire, the Assessment Tool provides the fraction of indicators affirmed for any dimension as a fraction of the total number possible for each of the maturity levels.
- The user can determine the maturity level of the dataset or what needs to be done to advance it to the desired level for each of the dimensions.

Using the Tool to FAIRify a Dataset

1. **Assess the dataset's current FAIR status:** Use assessment tool to evaluate the dataset's maturity against the five levels derived from the reported indicators
2. **Identify areas for improvement:** Based on the indicator assessment, pinpoint specific areas where the dataset needs to be improved to achieve a higher level of maturity
3. **Plan FAIRification activities:** Develop a plan (using a FAIRification Framework) to address the identified gaps in maturity
4. **Iterate:** Regularly reassess the dataset's FAIR status after each FAIRification cycle to track progress and make necessary adjustments

Sample Assessment Tool Output

Based on this assessment, 10 indicators still need to be satisfied for your Datasets to reach Maturity Level 1

- [DSM-1-R2] Data intended for sharing and reuse have a purposely defined representation as Datasets
- [DSM-1-R5] Dataset(s) available in Machine Readable Format
- [DSM-1-R0] Dataset Metadata is formally represented in the form of an identifiable Dataset Descriptor
- [DSM-1-R3] A representation of the Dataset Descriptor conforming to a relevant General Purpose Metadata Schema is available
- [DSM-1-R4] Dataset Descriptor is available in Machine Readable Format
- [DSM-1-R1] Contextual Metadata is represented at summary level and reported in the Dataset Descriptor
- [DSM-1-C0] Each Dataset purposed for sharing and re-use is assigned a unique Identifier
- [DSM-1-C1] Dataset Descriptor(s) Includes Descriptive Study/Project-Level summary information
- [DSM-1-C2] Dataset Descriptor(s) Includes Identifying & Descriptive Dataset-Level metadata
- [DSM-1-C3] Dataset Descriptor(s) contains access information for the Dataset
- [DSM-1-H1] Metadata hosting environment stores and maintains an identifiable Dataset Descriptor for each identifiable Dataset
- [DSM-1-H2] The Dataset and Its Descriptor are indexed and retrievable (in the same or separate hosting environments) via unique and persistent identifiers
- [DSM-1-H3] Retrieval of the Dataset and the Dataset Descriptor utilises a standardized communication protocol that is open, free and universally implementable
- [DSM-1-H4] Metadata hosting environment offers the capability to browse and search contents of the Dataset Descriptor

Based on this assessment, 19 indicators still need to be satisfied for your Datasets to reach Maturity Level 2

- [DSM-1-R2] Data intended for sharing and reuse have a purposely defined representation as Datasets
- [DSM-2-R2] Dataset(s) are standardised to a locally defined Dataset Model suitable for data sharing and re-use
- [DSM-1-R5] Dataset(s) available in Machine Readable Format
- [DSM-1-R0] Dataset Metadata is formally represented in the form of an identifiable Dataset Descriptor
- [DSM-2-R3] Dataset Descriptor(s) adopt a Metadata Schema representation that describes the locally defined Dataset Model including its structural metadata (i.e. Field-level and Value-level metadata)
- [DSM-1-R4] Dataset Descriptor is available in Machine Readable Format
- [DSM-2-R4] A formal documentation of the locally defined Domain Model is available in a Human Readable Format
- [DSM-2-R1] Contextual Metadata is formally represented and reported in the form of a locally defined Domain Model
- [DSM-2-C2] Where applicable, data is structured in the Dataset according to the Tidy Data Principles
- [DSM-2-C3] Dataset(s) Include Reference Fields that enable joining related datasets
- [DSM-2-C0] Where applicable, Dataset Field Values are standardised against a locally defined Data Dictionary within and across related Datasets
- [DSM-2-C1] The locally defined Domain Model contains concepts that describes the overall project/study design, the relationships between the Datasets, the key entities reported within the Datasets and the relationships between them.
- [DSM-1-C2] Dataset Descriptor(s) Includes Identifying & Descriptive Dataset-Level metadata
- [DSM-1-C3] Dataset Descriptor(s) contains access information for the Dataset
- [DSM-2-C5] Dataset Descriptor includes reference to related Datasets and if applicable the relevant joining Dataset Fields
- [DSM-2-C6] Dataset Descriptor includes Field-level Metadata as prescribed by a locally defined Dataset Model
- [DSM-2-C7] Dataset Descriptor includes Value-level Metadata or if applicable includes a reference to a locally defined Data Dictionary
- [DSM-2-H1] The Data hosting environment's Persistence Model is aligned with a locally defined Domain Model to enable interpretation of Datasets
- [DSM-1-H3] Retrieval of the Dataset and the Dataset Descriptor utilises a standardized communication protocol that is open, free and universally implementable
- [DSM-2-H2] Metadata hosting environment provides programmatic access and retrieval (API) for the Dataset Descriptor
- [DSM-2-H3] Data hosting environment offers the capability to browse and search related Datasets

Assessment Tool Output in Terms of Each of the Dimensions

Level	Representation & Format	Content & Context	Hosting Environment Capabilities	Overall Level % Completion
Level 1	33%	25%	25%	29%
Level 2	13%	0%	25%	10%
Level 3	13%	0%	0%	5%
Level 4	17%	0%	0%	7%
Level 5	0%	0%	0%	0%

Module 2 Supplementary Information

- The [FAIRplus Dataset Maturity \(DSM\) Model](#) is intended as a comprehensive reference model for state-of-FAIRness improvement in research datasets. Three different levels of data granularity are referred to by the FAIRplus-DSM model indicators when referring to the dataset model: dataset level, dataset field level, and value-set level.
- In the FAIRplus DSM Model, three dimensions are assessed using the following set of [indicators](#):
- The [FAIRplus DSM Data Model](#) provides a comprehensive framework for managing datasets in a FAIR-compliant manner.
- The maturity levels of a dataset or data using the FAIRplus-DSM Model may be accomplished by using the [FAIR Dataset Maturity \(FAIR-DSM\) Assessment Tool](#), which is the reference implementation for determining all five components in the three dimensions of the dataset maturity model.
 - Consulting the [glossary for the model](#) should provide additional clarity if needed.
- FAIRification Framework Phase Tips
 - FAIRification Phase: Goals
 - Have a goal in mind for your dataset? Start with the [FAIR wizard](#).
 - Have a dataset but do not have a clear idea of how it could be improved? Start with the [DataSet Maturity tool](#).
 - Not sure which of these routes is best for you? Have a look at the [recipe about the FAIRification framework](#) in the FAIR Cookbook.
 - FAIRification Phase: Project Examination
 - Examine in detail a dataset's current and expected data requirements as well as available resources and expertise.
 - Every task should be linked to a [FAIR indicator](#), which will specify the actions to be taken but also help identify the expertise needed to fulfil it. In addition, these tasks are expected to have varying levels of complexity depending on [the maturity level](#) targeted for the dataset.
 - Assign a priority based on what needs to be completed first.
 - FAIRification Phase: Cycle
 - This phase typically consists of multiple FAIRification cycles applied in an iterative fashion, with each FAIRification cycle focusing on a single FAIRification goal.
 - FAIRification Phase: FAIRification
 - Review outcomes and assess the success against the original goals. In this final phase, the cumulative outputs of all the FAIRification processes should be compared to the initial project goals, to assess the overall success of the process. This should include another assessment of your dataset with the [FAIR DSM tool](#).

Module 3

About the CARE Project

- [CARE PROJECT](#): The goal of the CARE project was to deliver treatments for the current COVID-19 outbreak as well as future coronavirus outbreaks.
- Part of the project focused on “repurposing,” in which drugs designed for other diseases are “repurposed” for a new disease.
- Since lot of work has already been carried out on these compounds, repurposing can deliver relatively rapid results.

FAIRification of the CARE Dataset

- The [CARE Datasets](#) are an excellent illustrative example to see the success of this approach to FAIRification. The goal of the CARE project was to deliver treatments for the current COVID-19 outbreak as well as future coronavirus outbreaks.
- The CARE project is committed to the FAIR principles of open science and will share its scientific results through open access platforms and peer-reviewed journals, as well as via relevant conferences and other events. The team will also work closely with other similar projects.
- Ultimately, CARE should both contribute to the world’s response to COVID-19 outbreak and ensure we are better prepared for further coronavirus outbreaks in the future.
- Using the FAIRification process, the CARE dataset maturity progressed from a “single-use data level” (level 0) to a “community level” (level 3) by improving *data access* and *discoverability*.

The Tailoring of the FAIRification Frameworks—CARE Dataset

FAIRplus Tailored FAIRification Process - CARE - Iteration 2

Individual Group Activity & Discussion

- Explore the data and organization of the dataset:
 - Screening of ~5500 FDA-approved drugs and clinical candidates for anti-SARS-CoV-2 activity.xlsx
- Assess the initial data maturity of the dataset using the FAIRplus DSM Assessment Tool
- Reuse the goals in the tailored framework that defined the project activities for FAIRification
- Perform a final assessment of dataset maturity, assuming the project actives were conducted and completed
- Compare your initial and final assessment of dataset maturity to those summarized in the tailored FAIRification framework for the CARE Dataset
 - Discuss any departures from those indicated in the tailored framework. Is there some subjectivity in the assessments?

Module 3 Supplementary Information

- We now look at one of the [CARE Datasets](#) in more detail with the intention of gaining practical experience working with the FAIRification Framework.
- The goal of the [CARE project](#) was to deliver treatments for the current COVID-19 outbreak as well as future coronavirus outbreaks. Part of the project focused on “repurposing,” in which drugs designed for other diseases are “repurposed” for a new disease. Because a lot of work has already been carried out on these compounds, repurposing can deliver relatively rapid results.
- By applying the FAIRification process, the CARE dataset maturity progressed from a "single-use data level" (level 0) to a "community level" (level 3) by improving data access and discoverability.

Appendix

FAIR Scientific Data

FAIR Data

- **FAIR Data follows FAIR Principles** These principles are widely adopted across disciplines and are applicable to data to promote transparency, reproducibility, and collaboration in research.

Impact of FAIR Data

- **Facilitates Data Sharing and Resue:** It ensures data can be easily shared and reused across disciplines and institutions.
- **Improves Reproducibility:** Well-documented and reusable data supports the replication of scientific findings.
- **Enhances Machine Actionability:** FAIR data can be processed and analyzed by algorithms, enabling automation and large-scale data integration.
- **Promotes Open Science:** FAIR data enables collaboration and transparency in research.

FAIR Data vs Open Data

- Data can be FAIR without being fully open. Sensitive or proprietary data can still adhere to FAIR principles by providing clear metadata and access conditions, even if the data itself is restricted.

FAIR Principles*

Findable:

- Data should be easy to locate for both humans and machines
- Metadata should be rich, standardized, and indexed in searchable repositories
- Each dataset should have a unique and persistent identifier, such as a DOI (Digital Object Identifier)

Accessible:

- Data should be retrievable using standardized protocols (e.g., HTTP or FTP)
- Access conditions should be clearly stated, including whether the data is open or requires authentication/authorization
- Metadata should remain accessible even if the data itself is no longer available

Interoperable:

- Data should be compatible with other datasets and systems
- Standardized formats, vocabularies, and ontologies should be used to ensure that data can be integrated and understood across different platforms and disciplines
- Metadata should include references to related datasets and resources

Reusable:

- Data should be well-documented and described so it can be reused by others
- Licensing information should be clear to ensure proper use and attribution
- Metadata should include detailed provenance information

*Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

What is Data FAIRification

- **Data FAIRification:** Activities designed to make data more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) to maximize its utility for humans and machines.
- **FAIRification Activities:** Task, plans for tasks, or actions to FAIRify data. A range of data types may need FAIRification.
- **FAIRification Process:** Process used to manage activities for Data FAIRification.
- **FAIRification Journey:** FAIRification and updates as needed over the lifetime of the data. Journey should be pursued to the degree needed for any specific intended use case.

Typical Data FAIRification Activities

- **Assessing Data:**
 - Evaluating how well the data aligns with the FAIR principles
 - Identifying gaps in metadata, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
- **Enriching Metadata:**
 - Adding detailed, standardized metadata to describe the data
 - Using controlled vocabularies, ontologies, or taxonomies to ensure consistency and machine-readability
- **Applying Persistent Identifiers:**
 - Ensuring the data has a unique and permanent identifier, such as a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) or a URI (Uniform Resource Identifier), making it easily findable
- **Ensuring Accessibility:**
 - Storing the data in repositories that support standardized access protocols (e.g., HTTP, FTP, or APIs)
 - Defining clear access policies (and ensuring metadata remains accessible even if the data itself is restricted)
- **Adopting Interoperable Formats:**
 - Converting data into widely accepted, machine-readable formats (e.g., CSV, JSON, XML)
 - Using standardized vocabularies and ontologies to describe the data and its relationships
- **Data Provenance:**
 - Providing detailed information about the origin, processing, and version history of the data
 - Including information about the tools, workflows, and methodologies used in generating or analyzing the data
- **Apply Licensing:**
 - Attaching clear licensing information to the data to specify how it can be reused (e.g., Creative Commons licenses)
 - Ensuring proper attribution guidelines are included
- **Publishing in Repositories:**
 - Depositing the data in repositories that support FAIR principles
 - Ensuring the repository provides indexing and search capabilities
- **Iterating and Improving:**
 - FAIRifying as is an ongoing process. Regularly updating metadata, formats, and documentation as standards evolve or new tools become available

What is Structured, Unstructured, and Semi-Structured Data

- **Structured Data:**
 - **Format:** Organized in a predefined schema (e.g., rows and columns)
 - **Storage:** Stored in relational databases or data warehouses using SQL
 - **Use Cases:** AI model training, CRM, BI, inventory management, SEO
 - **Pros:** Easy to use, accessible, works well with machine learning, abundant tools
 - **Cons:** Limited flexibility and storage options, rigid schemas
- **Unstructured Data:**
 - **Format:** No predefined schema; includes textual (emails, social media posts) and nontextual data (images, videos, IoT sensor data)
 - **Storage:** Stored in nonrelational databases or data lakes
 - **Use Cases:** Generative AI, sentiment analysis, predictive analytics, chatbot analysis
 - **Pros:** Flexible, fast accumulation, cheap storage options
 - **Cons:** Requires expertise, specialized tools, and data cleaning due to inconsistencies
- **Semi-Structured Data:**
 - **Format:** A hybrid between structured and unstructured data, using metadata for organization (e.g., JSON, XML, CSV files)
 - **Use Cases:** Web scraping, data integration
 - **Example:** Emails with standardized headers but unstructured content

What is Big Data

- Big data refers to extremely large and complex data sets that traditional data processing systems struggle to handle.
- It encompasses structured, semi-structured, and unstructured data, and its analysis can reveal valuable insights for organizations.
- Characteristic of Big Data
 - **Large Volume:** Big data is characterized by massive amounts of data, often growing exponentially over time.
 - **High Velocity:** Data is generated and collected at a rapid pace, requiring real-time or near real-time processing.
 - **Complex Variety:** Big data includes diverse data types, such as structured data (databases), unstructured data (social media posts, images, videos), and semi-structured data (logs, XML files).
 - **Difficult to Process:** Traditional data processing tools and systems are often inadequate for handling the volume, velocity, and variety of big data.
- Examples: Data generated by the Human Genome Project, Cancer Research, Medical Records, Wearable Health Devices, Microbiome Studies, Human Connectome Projects, Disease Surveillance, Drug Discovery, Biodiversity Monitoring, etc.

Data Types That May Need FAIRification

- **Structured Data:**
 - Tabular data (e.g., spreadsheets, databases)
 - Relational databases
- **Unstructured Data:**
 - Text documents, reports, and publications
 - Multimedia files (e.g., images, videos, audio)
- **Semi-Structured Data:**
 - JSON, XML, RDF (Resource Description Framework)
- **Big Data:**
 - Large-scale datasets generated by sensors, IoT devices, or simulations
- **Metadata:**
 - Descriptive information about datasets (e.g., authorship, licensing, provenance)
- **Linked Data:**
 - Data that is interconnected using semantic web technologies (e.g., RDF triples)

Value of Persistent Identifiers (PIDs)

- **Persistent identifiers (PIDs):** Long-lasting references to digital objects, resources, or entities that remain stable over time, even if the objects' location or other metadata changes.
 - Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) are a subset of PIDs for uniquely identifying digital objects.
- **Value of PIDs:** Used to ensure reliable access to resources and to prevent issues like broken links or lost information, which can occur when URLs to data or other identifiers change.
- **Organizations Providing PIDs:**
 - [Crossref](#): Links research objects, entities, and actions
 - [DataCite](#): Provides persistent identifiers for research outputs
 - [Research Resource Identifiers \(RRID\)](#): Tracks and verifies the resources used in research
 - [Research Activity Identifier \(RAID\)](#): Comprehensive record of the project and outputs
 - [Research Organization Registry \(ROR\)](#): Provides a PID for research organizations
 - [Open Researcher and Contributor ID \(ORCID\)](#): Persistent identifiers for researchers

Appendix Supplementary Information

- The concepts behind FAIRification of data are originally rooted in the [FAIR Guiding Principles](#), which were introduced in 2016 to improve the *management and stewardship* of data, particularly in scientific research. To learn more about data FAIRification, please see [FAIR in action - a flexible framework to guide FAIRification](#).
- [Persistent identifiers \(PID\)](#) are an important part of the FAIRification process. To learn more about PIDs, check out [NOAA Library](#).
- [ELIXIR's Resource Data Management \(RDM\) Kit](#), can be used by stakeholders to unlock the potential of their data, fostering innovation, collaboration, and discovery.

Acknowledgements and Disclaimers

The content for this course was based on materials developed for and insights gained from the [W1 FAIRification Lab: Applying FAIR Principles to Enhance Data Stewardship workshop](#), conducted at the [BIO.IT World Conference](#) in April 2025 in Boston, Massachusetts.

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